

Supplement

The attached maps complement the article:

Landeck, I. & Hildmann, C. (2022): Risk map for the spread of black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) into dry biotopes valuable for nature conservation in the state of Brandenburg, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.6460638](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6460638)

- Key**
- Dry grasslands
 - 1 very high risk
 - 2 high risk
 - 3 increased risk
 - 4 low risk
 - 5 no risk
 - Biotopes with black locust
 - 50 m buffer zone around dry grassland
 - 100 m buffer zone around dry grassland
 - 500 m buffer zone around dry grassland
 - Biotopes promoting spread of black locust
 - District boundary
 - Running waters
 - Settlements

Risk of Invasion of Black Locust on Dry Grasslands in Brandenburg

Barnim

Forschungsinstitut für Bergbaufolgelandschaften e.V.
as at 16/06/2021

Project InvaRo - Assessment of the Invasiveness Potential of Black Locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) in Brandenburg

Gefördert durch:

aufgrund eines Beschlusses des Deutschen Bundestages

Data basis:
Biotope mapping: Landesumweltamt Brandenburg, data until 15/01/202, dl-de/by-2-0
Running waters: Landesumweltamt Brandenburg
Settlements, roads: © GeoBasis-DE / BKG 2021
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Dahme-Spreewald

Forschungsinstitut für Bergbau-
folgelandschaften e.V.
as at 16/06/2021

Project InvaRo - Assessment of
the Invasiveness Potential of
Black Locust (*Robinia
pseudoacacia*) in Brandenburg

Gefördert durch:

- Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft
- Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz und nukleare Sicherheit

aufgrund eines Beschlusses des Deutschen Bundestages

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Elbe-Elster

Forschungsinstitut für Bergbaufolgelandschaften e.V. as at 16/06/2021

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Risk of Invasion of Black Locust on Dry Grasslands in Brandenburg

Havelland

Forschungsinstitut für Bergbaufolgelandschaften e.V.
as at 16/06/2021

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Märkisch-Oderland

Forschungsinstitut für Bergbaufolgelandschaften e.V. as at 16/06/2021

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Uckermark

Ostprignitz-Ruppin

Oberhavel

Havelland

Risk of Invasion of Black Locust on Dry Grasslands in Brandenburg

Oberhavel

Forschungsinstitut für Bergbaufolgelandschaften e.V. as at 16/06/2021

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350000 360000 370000 380000 390000 5830000 5840000 5850000 5860000 5870000 5880000 5890000 5900000

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Oberspreewald-Lausitz

Forschungsinstitut für Bergbaufolgelandschaften e.V. as at 16/06/2021

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Oder-Spree

Forschungsinstitut für Bergbaufolgelandschaften e.V. as at 16/06/2021

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Ostprignitz-Ruppin

Forschungsinstitut für Bergbau-
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Waldklimafonds
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Potsdam-Mittelmark

Forschungsinstitut für Bergbaufolgelandschaften e.V.
as at 16/06/2021

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Prignitz

Forschungsinstitut für Bergbaufolgelandschaften e.V. as at 16/06/2021

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Spree-Neiße

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0 2 4 6 8 10 km

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Teltow-Fläming

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Uckermark

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